

NEEDS ANALYSIS FOR THE EVALUATION OF TEACHER TRAINING PROGRAMS WITHIN THE MINISTRY OF RELIGIOUS AFFAIRS IN MALUKU AND NORTH MALUKU PROVINCES

Arsyil Waritsman ^{1*}, Theresia Laurens ², Izaak Hendrik Wenno ³

¹Universitas Pattimura, Ambon City

²Universitas Pattimura, Ambon City

³Universitas Pattimura, Ambon City

E-mail: arsyil.waritsman@gmail.com ^{1*}, thlaurens17@gmail.com ², wennoiz@yahoo.co.id ³

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Abstract

This study aims to (1) Identify the evaluation needs of teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces; (2) Analyze the factors that influence evaluation needs in the context of the island provinces; and (3) Describe the evaluation practices that have been implemented and examine the extent to which these practices meet the identified evaluation needs. The method used in this study is qualitative. The subjects in this study were two teachers. The data collection techniques used were non-test methods, including interviews and document analysis. Data analysis was carried out through three stages, namely: (1) Data Reduction, (2) Data Display, and (3) Conclusion Drawing and data verification. The results of the study indicate that (1) Teachers within the Ministry of Religious Affairs require systematic, continuous and comprehensive evaluation of training programs; (2) The need for teacher training evaluation is significantly influenced by the context of the island region such as geographical factors, limited electricity and internet infrastructure, and sea transportation constraints that affect the implementation and evaluation models that can be applied and (3) Current teacher training evaluation practices are still oriented towards process evaluation and participant satisfaction. The research findings are expected to provide contextual recommendations for developing teacher-training evaluation models that are relevant to the characteristics of the Maluku and North Maluku regions, as well as further strengthening the evaluation system within the Ministry of Religion.

Keywords: *Evaluation, Maluku, Needs analysis, North Maluku, Teacher training*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of education is one of the strategic aspects in national development (Rahayu et al., 2024). In achieving quality education, teachers, as facilitators, play a central and crucial role in ensuring the attainment of national education goals. To realize this goal, one of the government agencies that is part of this is the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, through work units spread throughout Indonesia, from the central level to the provincial level, including the Maluku and North Maluku Provinces, which are expected to organize training programs in an effort to develop human resource competencies. In its development, the training program should not be limited to the training implementation stage; it should also be continued into the evaluation stage to ensure that the program is implemented according to plan and in line with predetermined organizational goals (Salsabila & Fadli, 2023). However, without adequate program evaluation, the effectiveness of a training program will be difficult to measure, and the implications for educational policies and practices will be suboptimal (Kusnadi et al., 2022; Muiz et al., 2024). Therefore, research on the analysis of training program evaluation needs for teachers within the Ministries of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces is relevant to ensure that the results of program implementation align with the established plan, enabling the achievement of the expected goals. Previous studies have shown that training program evaluation has become a trend in recent years. For example, research conducted on training evaluation using the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model by Salamah & Istiyono(2022) found that the context aspect of training helps teachers develop their professionalism and competence, and the product aspect showed changes in teaching methods even though the training was conducted entirely online. On the other hand, a study by Yu-Yin Hsu dan Chin-Hsi Lin (2020) showed that technology-based training and the

SQD (Synthesis of Qualitative Data) strategy influenced prospective teachers' knowledge and attitudes toward technology utilization. Furthermore, a systematic literature review on training program evaluation conducted by Raihan et al (2024) found that training programs aimed at improving the competence of early childhood education (PAUD) teachers were effective when implemented comprehensively, sustainably, and contextually. Key factors influencing program success include teacher motivation, teacher competence, and institutional support. From a program evaluation theory perspective, the CIPP model developed by Daniel L. Stufflebeam is one of the evaluation frameworks widely used in program evaluation research in education (Rusniyati, 2021). This model emphasizes the importance of evaluating Context (Needs and Environment), Input (Resources), Process (Implementation), and Product (Results), which can assist in conducting systematic and comprehensive analysis to identify strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities for future improvement (Salamah & Istiyono, 2022). Furthermore, a literature review on needs analysis confirms that without proper needs mapping, teacher performance evaluation and training programs will not run optimally or effectively. This aligns with a study by Usman et al (2023) on needs analysis for teacher performance evaluation, which found that many teacher performance evaluation practices do not follow adequate procedures.

In relation to the needs analysis for training evaluation, in-depth research is urgently needed, especially for Islamic school teachers in the Ministry of Religious Affairs areas of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces, given the specific conditions in those regions. These specific conditions include the archipelago's geographic and demographic characteristics, unique educational challenges, limited infrastructure, and social and religious diversity. In this context, the implemented teacher training program should be evaluated qualitatively to assess its needs and implementation, and aligned with the realities on the ground. However, little research has been conducted that focuses specifically on the evaluation aspects of teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs in eastern Indonesia, and even less has linked the evaluation needs component to the context of archipelagic regions such as the provinces of Maluku and North Maluku. Fundamentally, this research has novelty aspects, namely (1) placing the needs analysis for teacher training program evaluation as the main focus, not just training program evaluation; (2) this research was conducted in two provinces that have diverse characteristics and contexts in the Ministry of Religion of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces so that it can produce a more contextual and island-based understanding; (3) using an in-depth qualitative approach to explore the views of teachers on evaluation needs where in general many previous studies have focused more on quantitative methods and have not explored needs qualitatively.

Based on the existing explanations, the formulation of the problem in this study includes: (1) What are the evaluation needs for teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces? (2) What factors influence these needs in the context of the island provinces? (3) How are the current evaluation practices for teacher training programs, and to what extent do these practices meet the identified needs?. These problem formulations serve as a basis/reference for conducting in-depth research to explore evaluation needs that remain suboptimal in the field. Based on these problem formulations, the objectives of this study include: (1) Identifying evaluation needs for teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces; (2) Analyzing factors that influence evaluation needs in the context of these island provinces; and (3) Describing evaluation practices that have been implemented and examining the extent to which these practices meet the identified evaluation needs. Thus, the research findings are expected to provide contextual recommendations for developing a teacher training evaluation model tailored to the characteristics of the Maluku and North Maluku regions, as well as to further strengthen the evaluation system within the Ministry of Religious Affairs. Overall, this research provides an overview of a system integrating needs analysis, program evaluation, and local context, a practice that has been minimally explored in previous research. Therefore, it is hoped that this research will not only have theoretical implications for teacher training evaluation but also provide practical contributions to training program managers at the Ministry of Religious Affairs and to education stakeholders in eastern Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Needs Analysis as the Basis for Training Program Evaluation

Needs analysis (needs assessment) is a systematic process for identifying gaps between actual and desired conditions as a basis for program planning and evaluation (Kaufman & English, 1979; Witkin & Altschuld, 1995). In teacher training, needs analysis is crucial to ensuring that training programs are aligned with teachers' competency needs in the field. Needs can be classified into normative, perceived, and actual needs, as determined by empirical data (Stufflebeam et al., 2000). Therefore, needs analysis serves as the primary foundation for determining the focus

and indicators for the evaluation of the teacher training program, ensuring that the evaluation is targeted and oriented toward quality improvement.

Teacher Training Program Evaluation

Teacher training program evaluation is an activity to assess the effectiveness, efficiency, and usefulness of a program in achieving its stated objectives (Arikunto & Jabar, 2014). Evaluation focuses not only on final results but also on the context, inputs, and processes of program implementation. The CIPP evaluation model developed by (Stufflebeam, 2003) is widely used in educational program evaluation because it provides a comprehensive framework for assessing program needs, planning, implementation, and outcomes. Furthermore, the Kirkpatrick model is also used to assess the impact of training on participant reactions, learning, behavioral changes, and final outcomes. Teacher training program evaluation is an important tool for decision-making and continuous program improvement.

The Context of Teacher Training within the Ministry of Religious Affairs in the Archipelagic Region

Teacher training within the Ministry of Religious Affairs has special characteristics because it relates to the competency development of Islamic school teachers and religious education. Teachers within the Ministry of Religious Affairs are expected to possess not only pedagogical and professional competencies, but also strong religious competencies (Basri, 2019). In archipelagic regions such as Maluku and North Maluku Provinces, geographical challenges, limited access, and disparities in educational facilities affect the effectiveness of teacher training implementation. These conditions require a training program evaluation based on a contextual needs analysis to ensure that the program is relevant to local conditions and teachers' actual needs. Therefore, a needs analysis for the teacher training program evaluation is crucial to supporting improvements in the quality of education within the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

METHOD

The method used in this study is qualitative. This research is an exploratory study. The subjects in this study were two teachers, each of whom came from representatives of teachers within the Ministry of Religious Affairs of Maluku Province and North Maluku Province. The research was conducted from October to November 2025. The data collection technique used was a non-test technique in the form of interviews and documentation studies. Therefore, the instruments used were interview guidelines and documentation study guidelines. The data that had been collected in the form of data in the form of interview results and documents related to the needs of the training program were then analyzed. Data analysis was carried out through three stages, namely: (1) Data Reduction; at this stage, the data was sorted to then determine which data was important information in this study; (2) Data Display; at this stage, the data that had been reduced was then described into an information/data presentation; and the last was (3) Conclusion Drawing and Data Verification; at this stage, the data that had been presented was then concluded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the need to evaluate the training program, interviews were conducted with two teachers, each representing teachers from the Ministries of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces. The interview with the research subject with the initials LR (Kemenag Maluku Teacher) was conducted on November 17, 2025, and with the initials ZS (Kemenag North Maluku Teacher) was conducted on November 18, 2025.

Data Reduction Results

The results of the data reduction are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Interview data reduction results

Number	Theme/category	Summary of statement by subject with initials LR, Teacher in Maluku	Summary of statement by subject with initials ZS, Teacher in North Maluku	The core meaning of the information obtained
1	Systematic level of training evaluation	Training evaluation generally ends at the end of the activity. After closing, the evaluation process is considered complete, so follow-up is no longer formally monitored.	Evaluations have been conducted, but they are not yet systematic and comprehensive. They are more informal, involving requests to share training results at schools.	Teacher training evaluation has been carried out, but remains limited to final activity evaluation and has not been continued systematically after the training.
2	Evaluation Aspects That Need to be Assessed	Evaluation should include understanding of the material, implementation in schools, and realization of the follow-up plan, not just attendance and graduation.	The evaluation covers materials, presenters, and training processes through questionnaires, but has not yet assessed the impact of implementation in the workplace.	The evaluation aspect remains dominant in the process and in participant satisfaction, but it does not optimally assess the results, impact, and implementation of the training.
3	Follow-up Action Plan	Follow-up plans are often purely administrative. Some participants implement the follow-up plans, while others do not, as they do not impact the final assessment or certificate.	There is no follow-up evaluation to determine whether participants actually engaged in socialization or implementation after returning to the Islamic schools.	Follow-up plans are a primary evaluation requirement that has not been seriously monitored and has not been used as an indicator of training success.
4	The Need for Local Context-Based Evaluation	Evaluations need to adapt to island conditions, electricity limitations, and technology. Online evaluation models are difficult to implement in areas with limited access.	Evaluation and follow-up of training were hampered by island conditions, weather, sea transport, and limited internet access.	Evaluation of training in island regions requires a contextual approach that accounts for local geographic conditions and infrastructure.
5	Alignment of Training Materials with Curriculum Developments	Training often lags behind curriculum changes. Islamic School teachers feel less facilitated than teachers under the Department of Education.	The training is considered relevant, but still needs to anticipate new policy directions and the need for an in-depth curriculum.	Evaluation is needed to ensure that training materials are aligned with curriculum developments and the actual needs of Islamic school teachers.
6	Stakeholder Engagement	The Islamic School principal plays a role in	The evaluation ideally involves Islamic schools,	Training evaluation requires the

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Number	Theme/category	Summary of statement by subject with initials LR, Teacher in Maluku	Summary of statement by subject with initials ZS, Teacher in North Maluku	The core meaning of the information obtained
		encouraging dissemination, but there has been no control from the Ministry of Religion or the Ambon Religious Education and Training Center after the training.	supervisors, the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the Ambon Religious Education and Training Center, and professional organizations such as the Subject Teachers' Council (Musyawarah Guru Mata pelajaran/MGMP).	involvement of various parties to monitor the training's impact more effectively and sustainably.
7	Factors Influencing Evaluation (Infrastructure and Technology)	Limited electricity, internet access, and technological understanding are the main obstacles to implementing and evaluating training.	Constraints on the Internet network and inter-island transportation access affect post-training evaluations and activities.	Geographical, infrastructure, and technological factors greatly influence the effectiveness of training evaluation in island regions.
8	Policy and Budget Support	Evaluation is generally not based on a specific budget but rather depends on the Islamic school principal's facility support.	There is no specific written policy regarding post-training evaluation, only verbal directions.	Strong and structured policies and budgets do not yet support training evaluation.
9	Evaluation Practices Implemented	Post-training evaluations were conducted through direct discussions to identify training needs.	Evaluation is conducted through a questionnaire at the end of the training, but does not continue after participants return to the workplace.	Evaluation practices are still limited to formative and reactive evaluations, and are not yet sustainable after training.
10	Benefits and Feedback of Evaluation	Evaluation impacts reflection on teaching practices and collaboration between teachers, even though it is unstructured.	Evaluation can provide input for improvement, especially through the suggestions column in the questionnaire.	The evaluation results have the potential to improve the program, but have not been utilized optimally and consistently.
11	Key Challenges of Evaluation	The main challenges include limited technology, access to electricity, and time and energy for follow-up assistance.	Challenges include time constraints, teacher coordination, and the islands' geographical conditions.	Evaluation challenges are structural and contextual, particularly in island regions and under resource constraints.
12	The Ideal Evaluation Model Expected	An ideal evaluation includes control of the follow-up plan, measurable feedback, and evidence of actual implementation.	An ideal evaluation includes a final evaluation and a post-training evaluation through monitoring, reporting, or online conferences.	The ideal evaluation model is a continuous evaluation that assesses the training process, outcomes, and impact in the context of the training.

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From the reduction results presented in Table 1, a mapping of the research objectives can be carried out (see Table 2).

Table 2. Identification mapping based on research objectives

Research objectives	Aspect	Main findings	General synthesis results
Identifying evaluation needs for teacher training programs	Evaluation needs	Post-training evaluation and follow-up plans are key unmet needs.	The need for teacher training evaluation leads to an evaluation that continues beyond the end of the activity. However, it assesses the implementation and impact of training in the islands' local context.
	Evaluation aspects	Need to evaluate implementation and follow-up.	
	Local needs	Evaluation must be adaptive to island conditions.	
	Parties' involvement	the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the Ambon Religious Education and Training Center, Islamic school principal, supervisor, the Subject Teachers' Council (Musyawarah Guru Mata pelajaran/MGMP)	
Analyzing factors that influence evaluation needs in the context of an island province	ideal model	Continuous evaluation from the end of training to implementation.	Geographical and infrastructure factors are the main factors shaping the need for contextual and flexible evaluation in island regions.
	Geographical	Sea transportation and weather hamper direct monitoring.	
	Infrastructure	Electricity and internet limitations affect digital-based evaluations.	
	Human Resources	Differences in technology mastery between teachers.	
	Policy	There is no written policy specifically for post-training evaluation.	
Describe the teacher training evaluation practices that have been implemented so far	Budget	Evaluation does not yet have a special budget allocation.	Existing evaluation practices remain administrative and formative, and have not yet reached a systemic impact evaluation.
	Evaluation implementer	the Ambon Religious Education and Training Center, Islamic school principal, supervisor	
	Method	Questionnaires, discussions	
	Instrument	Satisfaction questionnaire and discussion	
	Utilization of results	Some of it is input, not yet structured	
	follow-up	Inconsistent and unmonitored	

Data Display

The Need for Evaluation of Teacher Training Programs

Current Condition of Teacher Training Program Evaluation. Based on interviews with both subjects, evaluation of teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs in the Provinces of Maluku and North Maluku has been implemented, but not systematically or continuously. Subject LR stated that training evaluations are generally conducted during the training and end at the closing of the activity. After the closing, the evaluation process is considered complete, even though participants have developed a follow-up plan. However, this Follow-Up Plan is no longer monitored through a follow-up evaluation. Meanwhile, Subject ZS stated that the evaluation was conducted through a questionnaire at the end of the training. In addition, training participants were asked to apply the training and disseminate its results to fellow teachers in Islamic schools. However, the extent of this implementation has not been formally evaluated. This explanation indicates that evaluation is still focused on the final stage of training rather than the post-training stage.

Evaluation Aspects Considered Necessary. Both subjects stated that training evaluation should not only assess the training process, but also its results and impact. Subject LR emphasized the importance of evaluating participants' understanding of the material, its application in Islamic schools, and the realization of follow-up plans. He assessed that follow-up plans tended to be administrative in nature because they did not affect the final training assessment. Furthermore, subject ZS stated that the evaluations carried out so far were still limited to the assessment of training materials, presenters, and participant satisfaction. Evaluation of the application of training results in Islamic schools or in broader forums, such as the Subject Teachers' Council (Musyawarah Guru Mata pelajaran/MGMP), had not been part of a structured evaluation system.

The Need for Locally Context-Based Evaluation. Both subjects emphasized the need for contextual evaluation tailored to the archipelago's characteristics. Subject LR explained that limited electricity and internet access, along with the islands' geographical conditions, impact the implementation of evaluation, particularly technology-based evaluation. Online evaluation is considered difficult to implement consistently because not all regions have adequate infrastructure. Subject ZS also stated that geographical factors, sea transportation, weather, and internet connectivity are obstacles to the implementation of evaluation, especially when involving teachers from outermost islands. This presentation demonstrates that training evaluation in Maluku and North Maluku requires a flexible, adaptive approach to the archipelago's conditions.

Stakeholder Involvement in Training Evaluation. Interviews indicate that training evaluation involves several stakeholders, but it has not yet been integrated into a clear evaluation system. Subject LR stated that the Islamic school principal plays a role in encouraging training participants to disseminate information to other teachers. Fellow teachers also informally conduct evaluations through discussions and reflections on learning practices. Subject ZS added that supervisors and professional organizations, such as the the Subject Teachers' Council (Musyawarah Guru Mata pelajaran/MGMP), can be included in the evaluation, especially when teachers disseminate training results through the Subject Teachers' Council (Musyawarah Guru Mata pelajaran/MGMP). However, the involvement of these stakeholders remains situational and has not yet become an official evaluation mechanism.

Factors Influencing Evaluation Needs in the Context of Island Provinces

Geographic and Infrastructure Factors. Both subjects stated that the islands' geographical conditions were a major factor influencing the implementation of the evaluation. Subject LR highlighted limited electricity availability at certain times and limited access to technology as obstacles to implementing interactive, digital-based evaluations. Subject ZS added that sea transportation and weather constraints also impacted the involvement of teachers from remote islands in evaluation activities, both offline and online.

Policy Factors and Budget Support. Interviews revealed that training evaluations lack written policies and a dedicated budget. Subject LR stated that evaluations rely more on the principal's initiative, specifically in facilitating learning resources. Evaluations are not specifically designed into budget planning. Subject ZS reported that instructions for dissemination were delivered verbally, without a written policy governing post-training evaluation mechanisms.

Evaluation Practices of Teacher Training Programs Currently Implemented

Evaluation Forms and Methods. Current teacher training evaluations include completing a questionnaire at the end of the training, direct discussions with the organizing team, and disseminating training materials to Islamic schools. Subject LR stated that the post-training evaluations she attended consisted of training needs discussions without the use of formal instruments. Subject ZS stated that questionnaires were used to assess training implementation, but no evaluations had been conducted after participants returned to their workplaces.

Utilization of Evaluation Results and Follow-Up. Both subjects reported that the evaluation results had an impact, but had not been utilized optimally. Subject LR stated that the evaluation results encouraged reflection and improvement of internal learning practices at the Islamic schools. Subject ZS assessed that the suggestion column in the questionnaire provided opportunities for program improvement, but did not always provide clear follow-up.

Conclusion Drawing and Data Verification

Based on the results of data reduction and data display, the following research conclusions were obtained:

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- **Need for evaluation of teacher training programs.** Teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs in Maluku and North Maluku Provinces have been evaluated, but these evaluations have not been systematic, ongoing, and comprehensive. Evaluations are generally conducted at the end of training through questionnaires or discussions, and have not been followed up with post-training evaluations that monitor the implementation of training outcomes in madrasas. The most prominent evaluation need is assessing follow-up plans and the impact of the training. Participants have developed follow-up plans, but they are not consistently monitored and have not become a primary indicator of training success. Therefore, teachers within the Ministry of Religious Affairs require systematic, ongoing, and comprehensive evaluation of their training programs, with a focus on monitoring the implementation of follow-up plans.
- **Factors Influencing Evaluation Needs.** The island context significantly influences the need for teacher training evaluation. Geographical factors, limited electricity and internet infrastructure, and maritime transportation constraints influence the implementation and evaluation of applicable models. In addition to geographic factors, limited written policies and dedicated budget support for post-training evaluations also contribute to suboptimal implementation. Evaluation relies more on the initiative of the principal and on individual teachers' awareness.
- **Current teacher training evaluation practices.** Current teacher-training evaluation practices remain focused on process evaluation and participant satisfaction. The instruments used are limited to end-of-training questionnaires and discussions. Evaluation results provide benefits through reflection on learning practices and the dissemination of materials within the Islamic school environment. However, their use is not structured and is not always systematically followed up to improve the program.

After concluding the data findings, the next step is data verification. Data verification is conducted to ensure the credibility and consistency of the findings by comparing data across subjects and themes, and by aligning them with the research objectives and documentation related to the teacher training program evaluation. Table 3 presents information on data verification between research subjects and documentation.

Table 3. Data verification between research subjects and documentation

Verified aspects	Subject LR (Maluku Teacher)	Subject ZS (North Maluku Teacher)	Document review	Verification results
Systematic evaluation	Evaluation stops at the end of training	The evaluation is not yet comprehensive	Detailed evaluation in training quality assurance documents, but has not yet reached all training alumni.	Consistent
Follow-up Plan	Not monitored	Not further evaluated	The follow-up plan is included in the training curriculum, but the technical implementation for monitoring its implementation has not been detailed.	Consistent
Post-training evaluation	still minimal	There is not any yet	Post-training evaluation has been conducted, but has not yet reached all training alumni because it was conducted on a sampling basis.	Consistent
Geographical factors	Limited electricity and technology	Transportation and networks	-	Consistent
Involvement of parties	Dominated by Islamic school principal	the Subject Teachers' Council (Musyawarah Guru Mata pelajaran/MGMP).	the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the Ambon Religious Education and Training Center, Islamic school principal	Complete each other

The verification results, as presented in Table 3, demonstrate that the findings from both subjects and the document review are mutually reinforcing, despite originating from different provincial contexts. Furthermore, cross-theme verification was conducted. The findings regarding evaluation needs, contextual factors, and evaluation practices demonstrate a logical, consistent relationship. The limitations of post-training evaluations and the lack of

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monitoring of the follow-up plan emerged repeatedly across various themes and can therefore be considered key research findings.

Next, the research objectives were verified. Verification of the research objectives is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Verification of the research objectives

Research objectives	Conformity with research findings
Identify evaluation needs	Answered through the findings of the follow-up plan and post-training evaluation
Analysis of island area factors	Answered through geographical and infrastructure factors
Description of evaluation practices	Answered through the presentation of evaluation methods and instruments

Based on the verification process, this research data has limitations, including: (1) Data was obtained from two subjects, so the findings are in-depth but do not represent the entire region; (2) Evaluation was conducted based on the experiences of the subjects as participants, not organizers; (3) These limitations do not reduce the validity of the findings, but provide context for understanding the research findings.

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that the evaluation of teacher training programs within the Ministries of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces is urgent, primarily because evaluations conducted to date have not been systematic, continuous, or comprehensive. Evaluations tend to stop at the final stage of training and focus on participant satisfaction, without being followed by monitoring the implementation of training outcomes in the Islamic school. This condition indicates that evaluation has not been utilized as an instrument for organizational learning, as emphasized in the educational evaluation literature, which views evaluation as a continuous process for improving program quality (Stufflebeam & Shinkfield, 2007). Therefore, the main significance of this finding is the gap between the ongoing practice of teacher training evaluation and the principles of ideal program evaluation.

The most prominent need identified was the evaluation of the training's follow-up plans and impact. Although the training participants developed follow-up plans, findings indicate they were inconsistently monitored and not used as a primary indicator of the training's success. It aligns with Guskey's (2002) critique, which argues that many teachers' professional development programs fail to demonstrate tangible impact due to a lack of evaluation at the implementation and learning-outcome levels. Thus, this study's findings extend the literature by demonstrating that the problem of weak training impact evaluation occurs not only in the general education context but also in Islamic school teacher training in the Indonesian archipelago. Furthermore, this study's findings confirm that the geographic context of island regions significantly influences the needs and models for teacher training evaluation. Limited electricity and internet infrastructure, as well as maritime transportation constraints, limit the implementation of ideal post-training evaluations. The evaluation literature to date has relatively focused on evaluations in mainland or urban areas with adequate infrastructure (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006). Therefore, these findings fill a gap in the literature by presenting a contextual perspective: training evaluation designs should be tailored to the geographic and social characteristics of the region, particularly in island regions that face significant logistical and accessibility challenges.

In addition to geographic factors, limited written policies and a lack of dedicated budget support for post-training evaluations also contributed to suboptimal evaluation implementation. Evaluations tended to rely on the initiative of Islamic school principals and individual teacher awareness. This finding reinforces the view of (Fitzpatrick et al., 2012) that the success of program evaluations is heavily influenced by policy support and institutional commitment. In other words, evaluations cannot be effective if they rely solely on individual awareness, without a clear regulatory framework and resource support. Current teacher training evaluation practices, which focus on process evaluation and participant satisfaction, predominantly emphasize the first level of evaluation in Kirkpatrick's model: reaction. Meanwhile, evaluations at the learning, behavior, and results levels have not been systematically conducted. This finding aligns with a study Avalos (2011), which found that teacher training evaluations often focus on participants' perceptions, without assessing changes in teaching practices or their impact on learning. Therefore, this study provides new insights that this problem also occurs in the context of Islamic school teacher training under the Ministry of Religious Affairs. Despite this, existing evaluation results continue to provide benefits, including reflection on learning practices and the dissemination of materials within the Islamic school environment. However, the utilization of these evaluation results is not yet structured and has not been consistently

followed up on to improve the program. This finding emphasizes the importance of evaluation as a basis for decision-oriented evaluation, as emphasized in the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model, which positions evaluation as a tool for continuous program quality improvement (Stufflebeam & Shinkfield, 2007). Overall, the findings of this study extend the discussion in the teacher training evaluation literature by emphasizing the importance of impact evaluation and follow-up plans in island regions and religious institutions. This study not only confirms previous findings but also provides new empirical contributions regarding how geographic factors, policies, and organizational culture influence evaluation needs. Therefore, the results of this study can serve as a basis for developing a more contextually grounded, adaptive, and impactful teacher-training evaluation model that improves the quality of learning in Islamic schools.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the evaluation of teacher training programs within the Ministry of Religious Affairs of Maluku and North Maluku Provinces has not been implemented systematically, sustainably, and comprehensively. Evaluations are still limited to the final stage of training and focus on participant satisfaction, thus failing to provide a complete picture of the training's effectiveness in improving teacher competency and the quality of learning in Islamic schools. This situation indicates a gap between current evaluation practices and the principles of training program evaluation, which are oriented toward continuous improvement. The most prominent evaluation needs concern the follow-up plans and the training's impact. The follow-up plans developed by training participants have not been consistently monitored and have not been used as a primary indicator of program success. As a result, the training has not been fully aligned with changes in Islamic school teaching practices. These findings confirm that the success of teacher training cannot be measured solely by participant participation and satisfaction, but rather by the extent to which training outcomes are implemented and have a tangible impact on educational units.

This study also concluded that the island context significantly influences the need for and implementation of teacher training evaluations. Geographical factors, limited infrastructure, and maritime transportation constraints are key challenges in implementing post-training evaluations. Furthermore, limited written policies and dedicated budgetary support for evaluations make implementation highly dependent on individual initiative and leadership from Islamic school principals. Therefore, teacher training evaluation requires a contextual, adaptive, and institutionally supported approach. Overall, this study emphasizes the importance of strengthening teacher training evaluation systems that focus not only on the process but also on the impact and sustainability of training outcomes. The findings provide an empirical contribution to the development of teacher-training policies within the Ministry of Religious Affairs, particularly in island regions, and enrich the discourse on teacher-training evaluation in the context of religious education. Based on the research findings and conclusions, it is recommended that the Ministry of Religious Affairs, particularly at the provincial and district/city levels, develop a systematic, sustainable teacher-training evaluation policy. This policy should include post-training evaluation standards, including mechanisms to monitor the implementation of follow-up plans and to measure the impact of training on teaching practices in madrasas. Furthermore, dedicated budgetary support should be allocated for post-training evaluation. This budgetary support is crucial to ensure the continuity of monitoring and evaluation activities, whether through field visits, mentoring, or the use of simple technologies appropriate to the archipelago's conditions.

With adequate budgetary support, evaluation will no longer rely on individual initiatives but will become an integral part of teacher training management. The Ministry of Religious Affairs is also advised to develop a teacher-training evaluation model that is contextual and adaptable to the archipelago's characteristics. This evaluation model could combine offline and limited online approaches, involve Islamic school principals as supervisors of the implementation of follow-up plans, and utilize teacher learning communities as a vehicle for collective evaluation. This approach is expected to overcome geographical and infrastructure constraints without compromising the quality of evaluation. Furthermore, it is necessary to strengthen the capacity of human resources, particularly instructors, training managers, and Islamic school principals, in the field of training program evaluation. Specific training on impact-based evaluation and the utilization of evaluation results for program improvement will improve the quality of decision-making and the overall effectiveness of teacher training. Finally, the results of this study can serve as a basis for further research to develop and test an island-based teacher training evaluation model within the Ministry of Religious Affairs. This further research is expected to produce a more operational and applicable evaluation model, thereby supporting the continuous improvement of teacher training and Islamic school education.

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